
APPLICATION OF WORKPLACE HUMANIZATION AND JOB EFFECTIVENESS OF BUSINESS EDUCATION GRADUATES IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study examined application of workplace humanization and job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Two (2) objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were stated, answered, formulated and tested to guide this study. Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study and the population consists of one thousand two hundred and eighty-three business education graduates in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State and the sample size of this study was two hundred and ninety-seven respondents drawn from the population with the use of Taro Yamen formular, hence simple random sampling techniques was adopted in this study. A self-developed questionnaire titled “Workplace Humanization and Job Effectiveness of Business Education Graduates Questionnaire (WoHuJEBEGQu) was used to obtain data for this study. In addition, the said instrument employed face and content validity, which was validated by experts in the study area and a reliability index coefficient of 0.81 was obtained using test-retest method of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). Mean and standard deviation was used to answer and analyzed the research questions while independent t-test statistical tool was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of this study revealed that prioritized work-life balance and employee’s recognition are the variables of workplace humanization that enhances job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State to a high extent. In addition, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent prioritized work-life balance and employee’s recognition enhance job effectiveness in the aforementioned institutions in Rivers State. The study

therefore recommended among others that management of tertiary institutions should encourage prioritized work-life balance of employees when the need arises so that they can carry out assigned tasks effectively.

Keyword: Application, Workplace Humanization, Job Effectiveness, Business Education Graduates, Tertiary Institutions

Introduction

Workplace humanization is an aspect of quality of work life balance that is increasingly being heard in the Canadian Industrial Relations Vocabulary. Even though much has changed in the work place over the years, there is a new awakening that work life needs to be improved much more. This new awakening calls for improvements in both extrinsic and intrinsic aspects, of a true humanization of the work place. It has evolved a real and continuing opportunity for individual and groups at any level in the organization to influence their working environment and to effectively participate in decisions affecting their work processes, product quality and output, thus, improving work life has been the focus of Canadian Trade Unions and Government. It is the realization that it cannot be done piecemeal by attending to the extrinsic aspects of technology, compensation, working hours etc. that effective change is an overview that takes into consideration the social as well as the technological factors that it cannot be done for the workers without their active involvement in the planning of improvement. The new realization maintains that a worker should be able to function at his place of work with dignity as an individual human being and derive satisfaction and a sense of accomplishment in his work (Kalburgi, 2017).

Workplace humanization in a very broad sense, regards concern for person and human aspects in managing organizations. It is oriented not only to obtaining result through people, but also, and above all, toward people themselves, showing care for their flourishing and well-being (Pirson & Lawrence, 2020). It addresses issues such as job security for the worker, which involves a feeling of freedom from fear and anxiety regarding present and future employment, equity of worker's remuneration, which has to do with how commensurate the remuneration received by the workers is to the effort he/she puts in at work.

Business Education programme as defined by Nwosu and Ojo (2014) is a programme of instruction that prepares the recipients with the necessary manpower skills and competencies that can enable the graduates meet the needs of societal development. The objectives of Business Education as stated by Koko (2010) are to equip the individual with relevant skills required in their occupation through training for success in teaching relevant vocation in higher institutions in Nigeria and also develop the individual for self-employment in relevant industries. For these objectives of Business Education Programme and other inherently benefits of education to be realized, there is need to ensure sustainable standards in the education system.

Education is nowhere without teachers playing a pivotal role in ensuring achievement in an educational institution (Nurharani et al., 2013). The University is a place where human minds are trained and knowledge developments are facilitated. It is a community of scholars and researchers, who are keen on improving the quality of existing knowledge or recreating as well as reinterpreting existing social, cultural, economic, scientific or technological findings. The university, like any other organization relies on its employees who work to stir up the activities/affairs of the organization in order to achieve its objectives and improve organizational performance. These employees are regarded as most important and tangible assets in the organization (Onyeizugbe & Orogbu, 2015). It is a popular knowledge that no

university will grow beyond the quality of human resources that constitute the teaching and nonteaching staff. This is because productivity lies within the employees' ability and commitment as well as initiatives to improve the sustainability of the organization, which are often ratified by management (Markos & Sandhya, 2010). Job effectiveness is the measurement of actual output or result against set goals. The line managers and leaders play vital roles by accommodating employees concerns so as to maintain organization performance (Kazimoto, 2016). According to Sutarto and Muhsin (2016), job effectiveness is a state in which human physical and spiritual actions are conducted in achieving results or consequences as they wish. According to Siagian (2018), finalizing the appointed timely work is the effectiveness of the work. The performance of universities in Nigeria is regulated by National Universities Commission (NUC), and this agency is saddled with the responsibilities of ensuring quality assurance of academic programs and providing framework for ranking the performance of universities against set criteria. According to the framework for measuring the lecturers' performance, a lecturer's job effectiveness is measured based on his/her research output, supervision, quality of teaching, evaluation, community services among others.

For instance, Hale (2018) simply defined job effectiveness as "Doing meaningful work in effective and efficient ways, while Wesley (2015) sees job effectiveness as worker's outcomes in achieving the organizational objectives in which they work. Also, Nurharani et al. (2013) viewed teachers' job effectiveness as how a teacher behaves in the teaching process, and it is known to be related to teachers' efficiency. Teachers' job effectiveness determines their qualities in enhancing and developing National Education growth. (Onwuachu, 2007) viewed job effectiveness as the dedicated conducts of lecturers in carrying out the official duties diligently. A highly effective business educator may be a researcher, a receiver, a creator and a distributor of knowledge (Modebelu & Kalu-Uche, 2013). Such a lecturer is a supervisor, a counselor, a facilitator, a guide, a technocrat, a motivator, a leader, a model as well as a manager. He/she ought to be pragmatic in sourcing lecture materials, updating ideas and issues, employing mutual learning techniques, encouraging participation in team work and contributing to knowledge creation.

The researcher's experience and observation shows that many business education graduates in Rivers State face low commitment in their organizations because of dehumanized work environment. Perhaps, the average business educators in tertiary institutions in Rivers State may not be sure of the security of his/her job if for any reason there is any health or economic challenge.

Supporting the above observation, Abiauzu (2020) posits that more than 60% of the Nigerian worker prefers security to other incentives in the work place, this figure highlights the low level of security of work in country that has Africa's biggest economy. The research further established that a large population of employees does their job in boredom and helplessness. It is therefore, not surprising that the work place continues to witness increase in labour turn over and alienation. Work-life balance involve how much control one feels over the number of hours put into work in comparison to the number of hours one makes available beyond the boundaries of work (Cathy, 2019). The balance between work and life activities and how it is achieved changes from one individual to another as it depends on when an individual feels satisfied both the job and personal life.

Work-life balance concept in its broad sense requires organizations/institutions to effectively integrate employee's work and non-work roles such that the levels of multiple-role conflict and the associated stress and job dissatisfaction are minimized or avoided.

Work-life balance is a method which helps employees of an organization to balance their personal and professional lifestyle. Ezedeen and Stephen (2017) averred that the subject to work-life balance strategies continues to get a great deal of attention across psychologist, academicians, researchers and corporate organization and this has led to growth in conducting new research continually as employees and employers try to demystify work-life balance definitions, concept and even attributes.

The authors in their study findings revealed that employees are often pre-occupied with work when not working, and when in the company of family and loved ones, experience an inability to be meaningfully engaged in non-work spheres. For many people, work has become cognitively inescapable in the sense that technological devices have further added to this pressure annihilator at the line between home and office, hence today, employees are available to their employer round the clock. Similarly, Cohen (2018) noted that work or life balance is not only about finding the physical time to attend to responsibilities and duties but more importantly it is about finding the cognitive space necessary to process, organize and respond to the thinking demands of life within a complex society. Cappelli (2019) argue that from the beginning, it is important to understand that work-life balance does not mean to devote an equal amount of time to paid work and non-paid roles, in its broad sense, it is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or fit between the multiple roles in a person's life. Although, definitions and explanation may vary, work-life balance is generally associated with equilibrium between the amount of time and effort an individual devotes to work and personal activities in order to maintain an overall sense of harmony in life. Work-life balance from business education graduates perspective is the maintenance of a balance between responsibilities at work and at home. Scholars have observed that educational institutions need to be aware of the changing needs of staff/employee and provide flexible work-life balance strategies in order to retain their employees. Also, organizations/institutions that seek to increase their staff morale, commitment, satisfaction and reduces source stress and problem at workplace must equally improve their ability to recruit and retain talented staff.

However, Blackson (2020) noted that with an increased participation of women in the workplace, women are able to fend for themselves resulting in upsurge of single parents, dual-earners couples and more involvement from working mothers. Owing to such paradigm shifts, economic changes, social demands and other factors, striking a balance between work and personal life has gradually come to the forefront causing friction between the employees and organization management and even among themselves.

Employees do not only want attractive pay and benefit but also expect that their efforts are valued, appreciate and treated fairly (Peter & Boateng, 2022). Hence, recognition is the timely, informal and formal acknowledgement of a person's or teams behavior, effort or business result that supports the organizations goals and values, and which is usually beyond normal expectations. Consequently, employee when recognized feels that their organization have human feeling towards them. Harrison (2023) averred that workplace by managers in the organization should considers recognizing these employees no matter how little. Employee recognition as a measure of work humanization is the acknowledgement, appreciation or approval of the positive accomplishments or behaviours of an individual or team. It also encompasses praise or a personal note of acknowledging achievements including small gestures that are important to employees. Recognition as a component of workplace humanization is regarded as an important tool in promoting employees motivation and organizational success, this is because employees are likely to be motivated to improve their

performance based on recognition and are also likely to be less motivated if organization neglects their contribution (Abdullahi, Hashim & Hamid, 2022).

In addition, Umeke and Owhondah (2021) asserts that when employees are recognized in the workplace like their other counterparts, they feel more connected and are likely to stay with their organization, thus being committed, this is because recognition strengthens the essential bonds of a culture that workers want to be part of. It is worthy of note that employees recognition as a form of work humanization is a crucial factor that enforces job satisfaction. Most employees consider investing money in benefits and increased salaries to improve happiness, while importantly financial input is not the only way to improve job satisfaction. Employees' recognition is the act of publicly acknowledging workers in the workplace for who they are and what they do hence with employee's appreciation, workers recognize each other and make the workplace feel more inclusive and human.

Abdullahi et al. (2022) contended that happy employees are more productive and being recognized gives them the feeling of job mastery and that they are a great fit for their role and for the organization/institutions, hence recognition can improve employees' productivity, enhance loyalty and promote collaboration. Similarly, Owen (2023) affirmed that employee recognition is an important part of any workplace because it improves morale, bring sense of positivity and appreciation and makes employees to be more committed in their workplace. Owen stressed that the main goal of employees recognition is to let employee know that the effort they put in their job and the work results they achieved are valued and appreciated for the benefit of retention. However, Peter and Boateng (2023) identify benefits of recognizing employee's in workplace which includes: Building posit, work environment, reducing employees' turnover rate, and improves retention, fosters organization loyalty and improve employees' engagement in the workplace. In the same vein, Owen (2023) supported the above assertion stating that employee retention makes them feel human at workplace, boost their productivity rate, improves morale and employee's happiness and helps with recruiting top talent. Owen also posits that when employees are not recognized, appreciated and acknowledge, it is then view by them as work dehumanization. Finally, recognition reinforces what employees want to see more of thereby allowing them to see more good work and better performance. Thus, many organizations have yearly formal reviews that provide employees with the insight they need in order to determine how to grow in their position or develop the skills needed to move up.

This study is anchored on social exchange theory propounded by Homans (1961) and Pfeffer (1983). This theory holds that human behavior and social interaction are basically an exchange of both tangible and intangible activities. It notes that behavioural compliance on the part of the individual is exchanged for something which is perceived to be contingent on the individual's behavior. It is exchange of benefits, giving others something more valuable to them than is costly to the giver, and vice versa. This mutually benefiting is important to all parties involved because in the long run the relationship produces maximum gain for the parties and the organization as well. It is argued that people in organizations engage in a self-interested exchange process with the owner of the organization and among themselves, and strive to maximize the benefits of such an exchange process. Parties in exchange process carryout a cost-benefit audit to determine the viability of the exchange relationship. Social exchange is composed of actions of purposive actors that presuppose constellations of their interests and resources. These processes are governed to reciprocal relations. Exchange is defined as social interaction characterized by reciprocal stimuli. It examines the processes establishing and sustaining reciprocity in social relations, or the mutual gratifications between

individuals (Ahiazu & Asawi, 2019). The basic assumptions of the social exchange theory are:

1. Theory is the rational man model
2. Actors in social exchange make choices freely in regard to alternative courses of action while guided by cost-benefit considerations.
3. Individuals establish and continue social relations on the basis of rational value maximizing choices.
4. Participation in the exchange relationship is largely a product of intrinsic rewards.
5. Rational choice and behaviours.

The social exchange theory is adopted as the anchor of this study because it is apt to the variables this study. This theory posits that the relationship between an employee and employer is a social exchange and that people in organizations engage in a self-interested exchange process with owners of the organizations and among themselves, strive to maximize the benefits of such exchange process. To accomplish this, the parties in the exchange process carry out a cost-benefit audit to determine the viability of the exchange relationship.

Statement of the Problem

The inadequacy of work humanization can account for poor performance in the organizations in Rivers State. One of the most fearsome challenges faced by workers currently appears to be job security. The crux of the matter is that workers are not given equity in their wages/packages and as a result of this workers in the sector are perceived or viewed as second class citizens and are therefore, not given the privilege of job individuation i.e they do not control what they do and how they do it. This scenario has resulted in lack of job security, no job satisfaction, boredom, job alienation, and loss of performance in many organizations/institutions in Nigeria. The researcher observed that business education graduates staff both male and female performance has remained a serious challenge in many organizations in Rivers State. Some of these graduates exhibit negative, indifferent, casual, nonchalant attitude to the timely discharge of duties across the organizations. In addition, business education graduates who promise the heavens and do not deliver to employers will not be trusted but those who clearly and unambiguously deliver will be trusted and valued, and the organization will attain its vision. Hence, the problem of this study put in question form is, to what extent do prioritized work-life balance and employee's recognition enhance job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study examine the extent application of workplace humanization enhances job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Specially, this study sought to:

1. determine the extent to which prioritized work-life balance improves job effectiveness of male and female business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. establish the extent to which employee's recognition improves job effectiveness of male and female business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. To what extent does prioritized work-life balance improves job effectiveness of male and female business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

2. To what extent does employee's recognition improves job effectiveness of male and female business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to give direction to this study:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent prioritized work-life balance improves their job effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent employee's recognition improves their job effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population of this study consisted of 1,283 business graduates working in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State which comprises of 403 males and 880 females saddled with academic and administrative responsibilities in all the aforementioned tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The sample size for this study consisted of 297 business education graduates, which comprised of 113 males and 184 females in the aforementioned tertiary institutions in Rivers State using Taro Yamane Formula. An instrument titled "Workplace Humanization and Job Effectiveness of Business Education Graduate Questionnaire" (WoHJEBEGQu) with a five (5) point Likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE-5), High Extent (HE-4), Moderate Extent (ME-3), Low Extent (LE-2) and Very Low Extent (VLE-1) was adopted for this study. The validity of the instrument, the researcher employed face and content validity methods. Thus, a test-retest method of reliability was adopted in this study. The research instrument was administered to 25 employees who are not business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The same instrument was re-administered to the same group after two weeks interval. Specifically, the instrument computed with Pearson Product Moment Co-efficient indicated a reliability co-efficient of 0.81 which was deemed reliably for this study. In all, two hundred and ninety-seven (297) copies of the questionnaire were administered. The researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze and answer the research questions while independent t-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. However, to determine the decision rule base on the questionnaire, item with mean ratings between 4.50 – 5.00 is regarded as Very High Extent (VHE-5), item with mean ratings of 3.50 – 4.49 is High Extent (HE-4), item with 2.50 – 3.49 is moderate Extent (ME-3), item with 1.50 – 2.49 is Low-Extent (LE-2) and item with 0.50 – 1.49 is Very Low Extent (VLE-1). In addition, to determine the hypotheses decision rule, any value of the calculated t-test that is greater than or equal to the critical table value at a given degree of freedom was regarded as significant and the associated hypothesis rejected, but if otherwise, the associated hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does prioritized work life balance improves job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviations of the Responses of Male and Female Business Education Graduates on Extent Prioritized Work-Life Balance improves their Job Effectiveness.

S/N	Statements			Male = 68			Female = 152		
				M	SD	RMK	M	SD	RMK
	Extent	Prioritized	Work-life						
	Balance:								
1.	increases productivity			4.72	0.87	VHE	4.65	0.90	VHE
2.	improves employees morale			3.84	0.55	HE	3.28	0.52	ME
3.	reduces turnover in workplace			4.02	0.65	HE	4.17	0.70	HE
4.	builds stronger relationship in workplace			3.70	0.50	HE	3.66	0.68	HE
5.	fosters fulfilled personal and professional life			4.20	0.72	HE	4.19	0.66	HE
6.	allows employees to be more focus on what they are best at			3.56	0.51	HE	4.10	0.70	HE
7.	reduces stress among employees			3.38	0.40	ME	3.20	0.43	ME
8.	increases responsibilities at workplace.			4.00	0.65	HE	3.69	0.57	HE
	Grand Mean			4.03	0.52	HE	3.85	0.58	HE

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2023)

Table 1 showed the grand mean responses of 4.03 and 3.85 for male and female business education graduates respectively. They rated that prioritized work-life balance improves job effectiveness of business education graduates to a high extent. The item by item statement analysis showed that item 1 with mean ratings of 4.72 and 4.65 for male and female respondents respectively were rated to a very high extent, item 2 with mean ratings of 3.84 for male respondents was rated to a high extent, while that of the female was rated to a moderate extent with mean rating of 3.28. In addition, item 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 with mean ratings ranging from 3.66 to 4.20 for both male and female respondents were rated to a high extent. While, item 8 with mean ratings of 3.38 and 3.20 for male and female respondents respectively were rated to a moderate extent. Furthermore, the standard deviation ratings ranging from 0.25 to 0.90 with grand ratings of 0.52 and 0.58 for male and female respondents respectively show that there is homogeneity amongst the responses, indicating a consensus of opinions.

Research Question 2: To what extent does employee's recognition improves job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses of Male and Female Business Education Graduates on Extent Employee’s Recognition improve their Job Effectiveness.

S/N	Statements	Male = 68			Female = 152		
		M	SD	RMK	M	SD	RMK
Extent Employees’ Recognition:							
9.	leads to greater employee’s engagement	4.63	0.73	VHE	4.70	0.78	VHE
10.	increases retention among employees	3.77	0.71	HE	3.96	0.66	HE
11.	helps create positive overall workplace	4.00	0.62	HE	3.84	0.62	HE
12.	encourages employees to strive for excellence	3.89	0.58	HE	4.06	0.65	HE
13.	boost teamwork and productivity	4.75	0.86	VHE	4.84	0.90	VHE
14.	motivate employees to put in their best	3.66	0.57	HE	4.52	0.78	VHE
15.	improves employees workplace culture	4.31	0.78	HE	4.07	0.70	HE
16.	creates supportive work environment	3.90	0.60	HE	3.99	0.63	HE
Grand Mean		4.20	0.66	HE	4.17	0.60	HE

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork (2023).

Table 2 revealed the grand mean responses of 4.20 and 4.17 for male and female business education graduates respectively. They rated that employee’s recognition improves job effectiveness of business education graduates to a high extent. Furthermore, the item by item statement analysis reveals that item 9 and 10 with mean ratings ranging from 4.68 to 4.54 for male and female respondents were rated to a very high extent, item 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 with mean ratings ranging from 3.77 to 4.31 for male and female respondents were rated to a high extent, while item 16 with mean ratings of 3.66 and 4.52 for male and female respondents were rated to a high extent and to a very high extent respectively. In addition, the standard deviation ratings ranging from 0.57 to 90 with grand ratings of 0.66 and 0.60 for male and female respondents respectively indicates that there is homogeneity amongst the responses, indicating a consensus of opinions.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent prioritized work-life balance improves their job effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 3: T-test of Mean Difference on the Responses of Male and Female Business Education Graduates on the Extent Prioritized Work-Life Balance improves their Job Effectiveness at 0.05 Level of Significance.

Gender	No of Respondents	\bar{X}	SD	Df	LS	t-cal	t-crit.	Decision
Male	68	4.03	0.52	218	0.05	1.50	1.96	Not Sig. /Accepted
Female	152	3.85	0.58					

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork (2023).

Table 3 shows that the calculated t-value of 1.50 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96. Therefore, since the computed t-value is less than the t-critical value, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent prioritized work-life balance improves job

effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Rivers State is hereby accepted. This implies that the stated hypothesis is not significant, hence accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent employees' recognition improves their job effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4: T-test of Mean Difference on the Responses of Male and Female Business Education Graduates on the Extent Employees' Recognition improves their Job Effectiveness at 0.05 Level of Significance.

Gender	No of Respondents	\bar{X}	SD	Df	LS	t-cal	t-crit.	Decision
Male	68	4.20	0.66	218	0.05	2.10	1.96	Sig. / Rejected
Female	152	4.17	0.60					

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2023).

Table 4 shows that the calculated t-value of 2.10 is greater than the t-critical value of 1.96. Therefore, since the computed t-value is greater than the t-critical value, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on extent employees' recognition improves their job effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Rivers State is hereby rejected. This implies that the stated hypothesis was significant, hence rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Prioritized Work-Life Balance and Job Effectiveness of Business Education Graduates

The result analysis in table 3 reveals that prioritized work-life balance improves job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State to a high extent. In addition, the result of the associated hypothesis shown in table 3 reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on the extent prioritized work-life balance improves their job effectiveness. This finding is in agreement with Ezedeen and Stephen (2017) who averred that the subject to work-life balance strategies continues to get a great deal of attention across psychologist, academicians, researchers and corporate organization and this has led to growth in conducting new research continually as employees and employers try to demystify work-life balance definitions, concept and even attributes.

Employees' Recognition and Job Effectiveness of Business Education Graduates

The result analysis in table 4 proves that employees' recognition improves job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State to a high extent. Also, the result of the associated hypothesis shown in table 4 also proves that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on the extent employees' recognition improves their job effectiveness. This findings is in consonance with Harrison (2023) who averred that workplace by managers in the organization should consider recognizing their employees no matter how little. Employee recognition as a measure of work humanization is the acknowledgement, appreciation or approval of the positive accomplishments or behaviours of an individual or team.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that prioritized work-life balance and employees' recognition enhance job effectiveness of business education graduates in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Also, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of

male and female business education graduates on the extent prioritized work-life balance and employees' recognition enhance their job effectiveness in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Management of tertiary institutions should encourage prioritized work-life balance of employees when the need arises so that they can carry out assigned tasks effectively.
2. Management of institutions should recognized outstanding employees in order to boost their morale and performance.

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